

Quantifying emissions from cold chain transport of apples to and within Norway

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ABSTRACT

Norway imports a significant share of its fruits and vegetables, contributing to transportation-related greenhouse gas emissions. This study maps the cold chain transportation networks of imported and domestic apples in Norway, assessing CO₂e emissions from the point of export to individual supermarkets. It represents the most detailed analysis of its kind, tracing the journey from specific export locations through main and regional warehouses to retail outlets across the country. The Norwegian food market is dominated by three major retail chains, each operating its own distribution system, often supported by a central third-party importer. Most transport relies on trucks, which raises sustainability concerns due to fossil fuel use and potential refrigerant leakage. The coexistence of main and regional warehouses increases transport frequency and energy consumption, particularly for perishable goods like apples. Improving transparency across supply chains is essential to optimise energy use, reduce food loss, and lower emissions. By improving cooling technologies, reform transport logistics, and integrating innovative sustainability practices, Norway's food sector can address growing cooling demands while advancing toward reduced carbon footprints. On average, refrigerated transport of apples in Norway emits 0.166 kg CO₂e per kilogram. Of this, 0.161 kg CO₂e/kg stems from transport, 0.003 kg CO₂e/kg from refrigerant leakage, and 0.001 kg CO₂e/kg from the refrigeration process. Under current assumptions and with the use of modern refrigerants, leakage accounts for approximately 2 % of total emissions. These findings highlight the importance of targeted interventions in transport and refrigeration to support more sustainable food systems.

1. Introduction

The global food system allows for availability of fruits and vegetables all year around. As a result, countries that rely on imports in addition to domestic production can maintain access to a sufficient variety and quantity of these products. Countries like Norway, with cold to temperate climate, rely heavily on the import of produce from abroad. The most productive crop lands are located in the lowlands in South-Eastern and Mid Norway but cannot meet the national demand of fruits and vegetables (Flaten and Hisano, 2007; Lombnæs et al., 2011).

To maintain high product quality and food safety along the whole value chain, products need to be stored and transported at cold temperatures. This means cold storage and transport post-harvest from the producing export country to the supermarket in the receiving import country (Han et al., 2021). Multiple publications state that transportation makes a substantial contribution to the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and energy demand in the life cycle of fruits and vegetables

(Bernatz, 2009; Bosona and Gebresenbet, 2018; Roibás et al., 2016; Svanes, 2012; Wallgren, 2006).

Depending on the product's origin, transportation can be a significant contributor to GHG emissions, especially in comparison to locally produced goods which often account for only a fraction of the GHG emissions and environmental impact (Michalský and Hooda, 2015). In literature, most publications focus on the life cycle assessment of specific product types, following the transportation of this type from farm to a specific step in the value chain. The scope lies often at "Cradle-to-Gate", hence ends before the product reaches the supermarket. Only few publications review the impact of multiple products at the same time and follow multiple transport routes (du Plessis et al., 2025; Michalský and Hooda, 2015). Related to Norway, to the best of our knowledge, no comprehensive study focusing on the entire transportation chain of fruits or vegetables imported from multiple countries, including domestic crops, has been published so far. The market situation and the unique geographical and population distribution in Norway lead to a complex and interconnected food cold chain system. In Norway, about

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Nomenclature		X_i	Intern auxiliary heat load factor, -
<i>Latin symbols</i>		<i>Abbreviations</i>	
A	Area, m^2	API	Application Programming Interface
D	Real transport distance, km	COP	Coefficient of Performance
E	Specific energy consumption, $kg/(tonnes\ km)$ or $l/(tonnes\ km)$	GWP	Global Warming Potential
EM	CO_2 emissions, kg	GHG	Greenhouse Gas
f	Respiration coefficient, 1/s	CO_2	Carbon Dioxide
$F_{EM,WTW}$	Well-to-wheel GHG emission, kg/kg or kg/l	CO_{2e}	Carbon Dioxide equivalent, considers also other greenhouse gases and converts them into the equivalent amount of CO_2
FC	Fuel consumption, l or kg	<i>Greek symbols</i>	
g	Respiration coefficient, -	α	Convective heat transfer coefficient, $W/(m^2K)$
LHV	Lower caloric heating value, J/l	δ_w	Thickness of the wall, m
m_{ref}	Refrigerant charge, kg	λ_w	Thermal conductivity of the wall, $W/(mK)$
P_{res}	Res. power refrigeration unit, W	ϑ_m	Mean temperature, $^{\circ}C$
\dot{Q}	Heat flow, W	<i>Indexes</i>	
t	Transportation time, s	amb	ambient
t_{year}	Usage time per year, s	aux	auxiliary
Δt	Time difference, s	l	Refrigerant leakage
T	Temperature, $^{\circ}C$	r	refrigerant
ΔT	Temperature difference, K	res	resulting
U	Thermal transmittance, $W/(m^2K)$	resp	respiratory
w_{CO_2}	generation of CO_2 per unit of Apples, kg/kg	t	Transport
W	Real freight weight, tonnes		
W_V	Freight weight capacity of a transport unit, tonnes		
X_a	Outer auxiliary heat load factor, -		

22,000 refrigerated trucks and 4000 shipping containers are used to import a total of 460,000 tonnes of fruit and vegetables yearly, which accounts for about 70 % of the total fruit and vegetable market in the country. In the specific case of apples, around 38,800 tonnes were imported, and 7900 tonnes were produced domestically in 2023 (Opplysningskontoret for Frukt Og Grønt, 2024). Given the scale and complexity of these transportation networks, a comprehensive assessment of the supply chain, particularly the cold chain transportation, is essential to accurately evaluate its climate impact.

The objective of this study is to investigate CO_2 emissions of the Norwegian food cold chain, hereby using apples as a case for the development of a comprehensive methodology to assess the environmental impact of transportation. As main aim of this study the (1) land and sea transport routes for imported apples to Norway, (2) their distribution from the central storage unit at arrival to regional distribution centres and further to supermarkets, (3) the emitted emissions and energy usage for refrigeration during transport are investigated. Moreover, the CO_2 emission of storage and transport of domestic apples will be compared to those imported. By precisely investigating transport routes, means of transport, storage and refrigeration temperatures, this study aims to give detailed insights about emissions linked to imported and domestic goods on the example of apples into Norway.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Goal and scope

To develop a methodology for the transportation and distribution of fruits and vegetables in Norway, this study included the total handled volume of apples, consisting of the imported and locally produced apples. Apples were chosen as they are sold in the second highest volume, after bananas. As apples are both imported and domestically produced in Norway, it makes them especially interesting to assess. The study used data available from Statistics Norway from 2023 and focused on the 3 main supermarket chains (further named chain A, B, C), which cover 96

% of the total market (Opplysningskontoret for Frukt Og Grønt, 2024; Statistics Norway, 2025).

2.2. Methodology

System boundaries and assumptions along the methodology development

For the development of the methodology, some system boundaries and assumptions have been set up along the way. Fig. 1 visualises a simplified supply chain. The coloured sections indicate the specific steps addressed in this article. First, the overall supply chain was broken down into four transportation steps:

1. First, the transport outside Norway for the imported goods was investigated (Fig. 1; light brown colour). As a starting point for the analysis, it was assumed that the transport routes start in the capital city of the exporting country and end in the main central warehouses in Oslo, unless more precise destination information is available. Transportation within the exporting country is considered only to a limited extent, starting from a predefined point within the country to account for its geographical size.
2. Second, the routing of the locally produced apples was investigated (Fig. 1; turquoise colour). Local products are typically transported from the farmers to one of the nine regional packing plants. From there, packaged apples are either directly distributed further to the regional distribution warehouses (West-coast) or through the main central warehouse Oslo. Transport from farmers to packing plants was excluded from the analysis, as the scope of this study begins at the packing stage and focuses on subsequent distribution. Therefore, earlier steps in the value chain were not considered.
3. From the central distribution centre in Oslo, the imported apples are further distributed to the regional distribution warehouses located all over Norway. Transport routes inside Norway between the main and the regional warehouses were identified (Fig. 1; purple colour).

Fig. 1. Schematic overview over supply chain with the different intermediate stations from production to consumer. The coloured regions show the scope of the study. Free icons used from www.svgrepo.com.

4. Regional distribution warehouses are spread across the country (Fig. 1; dark brown colour). In this approach, it was assumed that apples are transported from each regional warehouse to the respective supermarkets in this region, to be then disposable for the end consumer.

2.2.1. Data collection

To gather comprehensive information on the Norwegian food system and its connected actors, this study used various methods to collect detailed information about the food system. When necessary, due to a lack of accessible information in literature (publications, reports, recommendations), grey literature, stakeholder engagement and primary conversation, news articles and media reports as well as unpublished information based on good networks and expertise within the field, helped extract necessary information.

Moreover, the data on the amounts of apples imported to Norway and the partner countries is based on the Statistics Norway (Statistisk sentralbyrå; www.ssb.no/en) online data base extracted with the available Python Application Programming Interface (API). The data about the supermarket stores of the three biggest supermarket chains in Norway was extracted from their website and translated to coordinates by the geocoder of Nominatim ([osm-search](https://nominatim.org/), 2025). Transport from regional distribution centres to the supermarkets was mapped based on most logical routes.

Data extraction and processing were performed with Python (Python 3.12) with the help of an ArangoDB database. The calculation of the street routes was based on the software Valhalla (Stepan, 2024) with the card material of open street map (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2017). The sea routes were calculated by the python package Searoute py (Halili, 2024). The map plots were mainly created with the python basemap package of matplotlib. The mean temperatures on the routes were calculated with the help of data from Copernicus Climate Change Service (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2019). The yearly mean calculation was based on the monthly average data of the temperature of air at 2 m above the surface.

2.2.2. Organisation of the distribution of fruit and vegetables in Norway

Norway has two main importers and three domestic distributors, which supply the products to the three main supermarket chains. The two main importers together account for approximately 96 % of the fruit and vegetable market in Norway, with one responsible for about 70 % of total imports and 65 % of domestic products, and the other handling around 25 % of imports and 30 % of domestic production (Bama,

2023a). Fig. 2 shows the share between the three major supermarket chains (A, B, C) investigated in this study and the distribution between their respective retail chains/ supermarket brands (e.g. 2A, 2B, 2C ...). 63 % of the total imported and produced fresh fruit and vegetables in Norway are sold in supermarkets. It can be assumed that this value is higher for apples, as the cultivation area for commercial apple production in Norway is limited to a few small regions and the growing phases are delayed by about 1.5 to 2 months compared to apple exporting countries (Ličina et al., 2024).

2.3. CO₂e-Modell

To calculate the CO₂e-footprint of the single routes, it is necessary to model the CO₂ emissions for the single sources. The following sources will be distinguished in this work:

1. CO₂ emission from Transport and empty runs EM_t
2. CO₂ emission from refrigeration EM_r
3. CO₂ equivalent emission from refrigerant leakage EM_l

2.3.1. CO₂ emission from transport and empty runs EM_t

The emissions originating directly from the transport was calculated through:

$$EM_t = FC \cdot F_{EM,WTW} \tag{1}$$

The equation consists of the fuel consumption FC and the well-to-wheel greenhouse gas (GHG) emission factor F_{EM,WTW}, taken from Table 1.

To calculate the fuel consumption the following equation was applied (Schmied and Knörr, 2011):

$$FC = W \cdot D \cdot E \tag{2}$$

With FC as the fuel consumption in l or kg, W as the real freight weight, D as the real transport distance and E as the specific energy consumption in l or kg fuel per tonnes km (see Table 2). The specific energy consumption considers certain amounts of empty runs as described in the work of Schmied and Knörr (2011).

2.3.2. CO₂ emission from refrigeration EM_r

The heat flow Q_{res} that is occurring in one transport unit is calculated with the following equation:

Fig. 2. Market share of the single chains and the supermarket concepts of the chains.

Table 1
Well-to-wheel greenhouse gas (GHG) emission factor $F_{EM,WTW}$ (Schmied and Knörr, 2011).

Fuel type	Diesel Germany	RFO (Residual fuel oil)
Unit	kg CO ₂ e / l	kg CO ₂ e/ kg
	2.94	3.39

$$\dot{Q}_{res} = \dot{Q}_{resp} + \dot{Q}_{amb} + \dot{Q}_{aux} \quad (3)$$

It consists of the heat production through respiration of the apples, the heat flow from or to the environment and the auxiliary heat flow from additional heat sources.

The respiratory heat generation per time unit of the apples is calculated from Becker and Fricke (1996):

$$\dot{Q}_{resp} = W \cdot 10.7 \frac{J}{kg} \frac{w_{CO_2}}{\Delta t} \quad (4)$$

With the generation of kg CO₂ per unit of kg Apples per time unit:

$$\frac{w_{CO_2}}{\Delta t} = f \left(\frac{9\theta_m}{5 \cdot C} + 32 \right)^g \quad (5)$$

With the respiration coefficients $f = 5.687 \cdot 10^{-4} \frac{kg \ CO_2}{kg \ Apples \ s}$ and $g = 2.598$.

The heat flow to or from the environment is calculated from the one-dimensional heat transfer through a plane wall:

$$\dot{Q}_{amb} = U \cdot A \cdot \Delta T = U \cdot A \cdot (T_i - T_{amb}) \quad (6)$$

The temperature difference was given by the temperature $T_i = 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ that is optimal for the apples to be stored at and the ambient temperature T_{amb} . The ambient temperature was calculated for every route from the yearly mean temperature averaged over the route. Here, it is to note, that the route coordinates were not evenly distributed over the route and the time that the different parts of the route take were not considered, leading to an average temperature, that is not the real average temperature, but the best estimate that can be made.

The thermal transmittance of the wall of the storage compartment of the truck/container was found with:

$$U = \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_i} + \frac{\delta}{\lambda_w} + \frac{1}{\alpha_o} \right)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Here is α_i the inner and α_o the outer convective heat transfer coefficient, λ_w the thermal conductivity and δ the thickness of the wall with the values shown in Table 3.

The surface area A of the storage compartment was taken in

dependence of the vehicle type from Table 4.

The auxiliary heat load was caused by auxiliary systems like the ventilation through the evaporator and was considered through a constant factor $X_i = 0.03$:

$$\dot{Q}_{aux} = X_i (\dot{Q}_{resp} + \dot{Q}_{amb}) \quad (8)$$

With the heat load it is possible to calculate the needed power of the refrigeration unit by assuming a constant coefficient of performance (COP) for cooling or heating and considering auxiliary power consumption because of the ventilation need of the condenser with $X_a = 0.02$:

$$P_{res} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{res}}{COP} + (X_a + X_i) (\dot{Q}_{resp} + \dot{Q}_{amb}) \quad (9)$$

The COP was assumed to be 2.0 for both heating and cooling. Although the COP for heating is typically higher than for cooling, a uniform value was used here to reflect a system primarily designed for cooling. From the needed power it was possible to calculate the CO₂-emissions caused by refrigeration:

$$EM_r = \frac{P_{res}}{LHV} \cdot \frac{W}{W_v} \cdot \frac{t}{t_{year}} \cdot F_{EM,WTW} \quad (10)$$

With the lower calorific heating value $LHV = 35.7 \cdot 10^6 \text{ J/l}$ (Schmied and Knörr, 2011), t as the transportation time and t_{year} as the usage time per year and W_v as the freight weight capacity of the transport unit from Table 4. It was assumed that the Refrigeration units are always running on Diesel.

2.3.3. CO₂e emission from refrigerant leakage EM_l

The CO₂ equivalent emission from the leakage of the refrigerant was calculated with:

$$EM_l = m_{ref} \cdot LR \cdot GWP_{100} \cdot \frac{W}{W_v} \cdot \frac{t}{t_{year}} \quad (11)$$

With the leakage rate per year $LR = 0.2$, the refrigerant charge m_{ref} as in Table 4 and the global warming potential of the refrigerant GWP_{100} over 100 years.

As refrigerants, there were three separate cases defined as can be seen in Table 5.

3. Results and discussion

The underlying sections describe the refrigerated transportation of apples in- and into Norway and follow the structure as described in Section 2.2.

Fig. 3. Comparison of the airline routes of the five main export countries vs. actual transport routes shown for apples based on (Kendler et al., 2025).

Fig. 4. Transport routes for apples from packing plants to distribution centres. Green dots representing the respective packing plants, red dots the distribution centres and different coloured lines the transport routes.

3.1. Step 1: apple import

In total, 46,693 tonnes of apples were consumed in 2023, of which 38,784 tonnes (83 %) being imported. The five biggest exporting countries were Italy (56.1 %), Poland (19.4 %), Chile (6.7 %), Austria (3.6 %), New Zealand (3.5 %), representing total 89.3 % of all imported apples (Opplysningskontoret for Frukt Og Grønt, 2024). Fig. 3 visualises the transportation routes from these exporting countries that were used

Table 2 Specific energy consumption for different vehicle types (Schmied and Knörr, 2011).

Type vehicle	Truck 7.5–12 tonnes	Truck 24–40 tonnes	Container Ship (Average)
Unit	l fuel / tonnes km	l fuel / tonnes km	kg fuel / tonnes km
Average goods	0.061	0.023	0.0051

in this work, showing transportation routes on land (Italy, Austria, Poland) as well as by ship from New Zealand and Chile. The means of transport and the lengths of the routes are shown in Table 6.

The apples from Poland, Austria and Italy are transported through Europe by truck (Becker, 2022) and already account for a share of 79.1 %. Given that Chile and New Zealand have a combined share of 10 %, and given the distance between these countries and Norway, this is a significant figure for intercontinental transport. For New Zealand, the apples were assumed to be transported by container ship over a distance of 21,508 km from Wellington, New Zealand to Rotterdam, where then a share of 10 % of them are transported by road for 1,607 km and 90 % by ship for 1,021 km to bring the apples to the main storage facilities in the Oslo area (Becker, 2022). Chilean apples were assumed to travel 13,982 km by ship to Rotterdam, after which they follow the same distribution route as the New Zealand apples to reach Oslo.

3.2. Step 2: distribution of Norwegian apples from packing plants to regional distribution centres

There are nine main packing plants for apples in Norway (Fig. 4), supplying all Norwegian apples to the three supermarket chains. The volume of domestic produced apples normally varies between 7000 to 9000 tonnes per year. For 2023, the volume of Norwegian apples was 7900 tonnes (17.6 % of all). Transportation of Norwegian apples are mainly done in September to December, but the last years, smaller volumes of Norwegian apples were in market until March due to storage in controlled atmosphere (Indergård et al., 2024).

The area where the packing plants are located represents the cultivation region in Norway, particularly the Vestland region, which alone has six of those packing facilities. From those nine packing plants, the apples are transported directly to the regional distribution centres. Most apples are transported to the main central distribution centres in the Oslo region. An exception are apples distributed in the West (Bergen)

Table 3 Data for calculation of heat transfer.

Variable	Unit	Value
α_i	W/(m ² K)	30
λ_w (PUR)	W/(mK)	0.025
δ	m	0.06
α_o	W/(m ² K)	100

Table 4

Data to the vehicle types. Values for the freight weight capacity of a transport unit, tonnes (W_v) for of an average good are based on [Schmied and Knörr \(2011\)](#).

Unit	Length m	Width m	Height m	W_v tonnes	Surface area m ²	Operation per year t_{year} hours	Charge refrigeration system m_{ref} kg
Truck 7.5–12 tonnes	7.2	2.40	2.50	3.6	82.6	1,760	6
Truck 24–40 tonnes	13.6	2.48	2.70	15.6	154.3	1,760	8
20 feet Container	6.1	2.44	2.59	10.5	74.0	4,380	6

Table 5

Refrigerants for the different types of transport.

Case	Marine transport	Road transport
Old	R134a (GWP ₁₀₀ = 1,430)	R404A (GWP ₁₀₀ = 3,900)
Modern	R1234yf (GWP ₁₀₀ = 4)	R452A (GWP ₁₀₀ = 2,336)
CO ₂	CO ₂ (GWP ₁₀₀ = 1)	CO ₂ (GWP ₁₀₀ = 1)

and Southwest (Stavanger), where the regional distribution centres get supplied directly from the packing plants. The volumes of apples delivered from each of the nine packing plants to distribution centres was found through an earlier project ([Indergård et al., 2024](#)) and varies from season to season, an average volume is presented in [Table 7](#). The transport mean for the emission calculation of the routes was modelled as “Truck 24 – 40 tonnes” (see [Tables 2 and 4](#)).

3.3. Step 3: distribution from central distribution warehouse to regional distribution warehouses

In this step of the value chain, most packaged domestic apples as well as all imported apples are located at the main distribution centres in Oslo. Apples get restocked, repacked and further distributed to the regional distribution centres in South-, East-, Middle-, and Northern Norway ([Fig. 5](#)).

The transport is done by semi-trailers and calculated as “Truck 24 – 40 tonnes” as defined in [Table 2](#) and following. Supermarket chain C has 13 regional distribution centres, chain B has 9 and A has 6. The regional centres are shown in [Fig. 6](#) and [Table 8](#) with the transported amounts originating from the Oslo main centre. The routes that were used in this work between the main distribution centre and the regional ones are shown in [Fig. 5](#).

3.4. Step 4: distribution from the regional distribution centres to supermarkets

The imported and domestic harvested apples are known in volume (tonnes), but the volume sold by each of the three supermarket chains is not known. The percentage of total market share for each of the concepts for each of the three supermarket chains was therefore used for calculating the volumes distributed from each regional distribution centre (see [Table 9](#)). The limitation of this method is that it is assumed that all supermarkets within one concept sells the same amounts of apples, either its north or south of Norway, in a city or countryside.

The overall turnover for the supermarket food market was in 2023

Table 6

Transport route from the five biggest apple exporting countries to Norway, showing route points (cities), means of transport (types) and distances [km] of each stop / transport type.

Source country	Route	Means of transport	Distances /km
Italy	Milano → Oslo	Truck 24–40 tonnes	2,278
Poland	Warsaw → Oslo	Truck 24–40 tonnes	1,916
Chile	Santiago → Puerto San Antonio → Port of Rotterdam → Oslo	Truck 24–40 tonnes → Container Ship → Truck 24–40 tonnes / Container Ship	114.5 → 13 982 → 1,607 / 1,021
Austria	Vienna → Oslo	Truck 24–40 tonnes	2,001
New Zealand	Wellington → Port of Wellington → Port of Rotterdam → Oslo	Truck 24–40 tonnes → Container Ship → Truck 24–40 tonnes / Ship	3 → 21,508 → 1,607 / 1,021

Table 7

Tonnes of apples distributed from packing plant to distribution centres.

Tonnes apples	From	To	Chain A tonnes	Chain B tonnes	Chain C tonnes
300	Innvik	Oslo	106		194
500	Leikanger	Laerdal			
200	Laerdal	Bergen	71		129
500	Laerdal	Oslo	177		323
405	Utne	Bergen	100	122	183
1,400	Utne	Oslo	494		906
200	Lofthus	Bergen	57	90	104
470	Lofthus	Oslo	108	112	199
100	Naa	Bergen	35		65
525	Årdal	Stavanger	106	128	191
100	Årdal	Oslo	25	30	45
2,560	Gvarv	Oslo	655	804	1,201
240	Gvarv	Stavanger	36	171	33
900	Lier	Oslo	318		582

Fig. 5. Transport routes for apples from main distribution centre to regional distribution centres.

Fig. 6. Location of regional distribution warehouses for chain A, chain B and chain C; the red dots in the specific zones visualise the regional distribution centres from which products are distributed within the respective zone.

Table 8
Volume of apples transported from Oslo to regional distribution centres.

Chain A	Tonnes apples	Chain B	Tonnes apples	Chain C	Tonnes apples
North (Mo i Rana)	1,018	North (Tromsø)	1,137	North (Tromsø)	641
Mid (Trondheim)	1,412	Midd/Nordland (Trondheim)	2,116	Lofoten (Sortland)	200
NorthWest (Molde)	657	NorthWest (Trondheim)	487	Midd/Nordland (Trondheim)	1,382
West (Bergen)	1,101	Vestland (Bergen)	984	NorthWest (Molde)	1,505
SouthWest (Stavanger)	662	SouthWest (Stavanger)	1,401	Vestland (Bergen)	2,100
South (Kristiansand)	772	SouthEast (Oslo)	2,462	SouthWest (Stavanger)	1,057
Telemark (Oslo)	1,412	Inland (Gardermoen)	1,248	South (Lillesand)	1,268
East (Vestby)	1,084	Oslo (Oslo)	1,562	Telemark (Larvik)	1,869
Oslo (Oslo)	1,904			VikenWest (Sande)	1,341
Inland (Brummundal)	690			VikenEast (Nordby)	1,570
				Oslo (Oslo)	4,715
				Inland East (Brummundal)	1,392
				Inland West (Fagernes)	452

17.9 billion €, where the fresh fruit and vegetables market was estimated to be 10.7 % resembling 1.9 billion € (Dagligvarehandelen, 2024). The total volumes of apples in 2023 were as mentioned 46,700 tonnes, where the three supermarket chains distribute 44,823 tonnes.

As previously described, the three main supermarket chains use different regional zones for the distribution of goods within those regions. Fig. 6 shows the difference in location, size and number of zones for the three supermarket chains. Chain A divides the distribution areas in 10 zones with 9 regional distribution centres, chain B in 7, with 6

Table 9
Tonnes of apples sold in average from each supermarket concepts.

	Market share in 2023	Tonnes apples	Nr. of supermarkets	Tonnes apple per supermarket
1A	23,80 %	11,115	678	16,4
5C	24,10 %	11,255	716	15,7
2C	3,30 %	1,541	439	3,5
1C	0,38 %	177	132	1,3
3C	6,50 %	3,036	282	10,7
4C	9,30 %	4,343	185	23,5
5B	17,30 %	8,079	579	13,9
1B	0,40 %	187	173	1,1
3B	3,20 %	1,494	259	5,8
4B	4,60 %	2,148	32	67,1
2B	3,10 %	1,448	65	22,2

distribution centres, and supermarket chain C into 13 zones with 13 regional distribution centres, respectively. The distribution within some of those zones include very long distances and supermarkets are supplied with fresh produce all the way to the far northeast close to the Russian border. These distances are challenging, with an average distance from the northern most distribution centres in Tromsø (supermarket chain B and C) and Mo i Rana (supermarket chain A) to the most remote supermarkets in Kirkenes, covering a road distance of about 800 and 1,000 km respectively.

The transport mean for the emission calculation of the routes was modelled as “Truck 12 – 24 tonnes” (see Tables 2 and 4).

3.5. GHG-emissions

Table 10 shows the calculated results of the entire distribution chain of the three supermarket chains together. Compared to the entire Norwegian CO₂ emissions in 2023 with 70.91 million tonnes (Jones et al., 2024), the in this study tracked CO₂ emissions of 7432 tonnes resemble 0.01 % of that number, with the note that the mayor part of the emissions do not take place on Norwegian territory.

As it can be seen from Table 10, a total of 97.3 % of the emissions are caused directly by the transportation, while refrigerant leakage accounts for 1.8 % and the operation of the refrigeration system itself contributes only to 0.9 %. Despite its small share, refrigerant leakage results in

Table 10
Results of calculation for entire chain.

	All	Transport	Refrigeration	Leakage
CO ₂ e / tonnes CO ₂ (modern)	7,432	7,233	63	137
Spec. CO ₂ e emission / kg CO ₂ /kg Apples (modern)	0.166	0.161	0.001	0.003
Share /%	100	97.3	0.9	1.8
CO ₂ e / tonnes CO ₂ (CO ₂)				0.1
CO ₂ e / tonnes CO ₂ (old)				288

substantial emissions due to the high GWP of R452A (HFC/HFO blend), summing up to 173 tonnes CO₂e. If older HFC refrigerants such as R134a and R404A were used instead, leakage-related emissions would nearly double to 288 tonnes CO₂e. On the other hand, if a low-GWP refrigerant such as CO₂ would be used, leakage related emissions would be reduced to 100 kg CO₂. This emphasises the importance of phasing out high-GWP fluids. Even though leakage represents a minor fraction of the system’s total emissions, its climate impact is disproportionately big. Which is why transitioning to natural working fluids like CO₂ or propane is important for effective emissions reductions, provided that the system performance is not compromised.

In Table 11 the equivalent CO₂ emissions caused by importing apples from different countries is displayed. The entire import to Oslo main distribution centre is causing 5,691.9 tonnes CO₂e and thus leading to a specific footprint of 0.1644 kg CO₂e/kg for imported apples. New Zealand has the highest footprint caused by the long transport over sea. Poland has the lowest because of the relatively short transport on road.

As can be seen in Fig. 7, supermarkets in Norway are spread out throughout the whole country, with a majority in the Oslo region in the South. Our calculations have shown that the specific CO₂e footprint of supermarkets in the far North is substantially higher than around metropolitan areas in the South. This is also reflected in Fig. 8, showing the CO₂e footprint specific for the three supermarket chains. This is due to the long road transport system with long distances between supermarkets and the zone’s specific regional distribution centre. Rail transportation was excluded from this study under the assumption that it plays only a minor role in Norway’s overall transport system and can therefore be disregarded. However, if road transport can be changed to rail transport, significant reductions in CO₂e emissions can be expected, and even more so if trains are operated electrically. Although the train system in Norway consists of only 4,200 km, shared by some main train lines, freight transport with train should be expanded. A study on upgrading the Røros line, a diesel-powered railway line and one of the main lines connecting mid-Norway (Trondheim and cities further north) with Oslo, indicates that an upgrade of more freight train routes is possible. One freight train could hereby replace 30 semitrailer trucks and even though not all lines are electrified in Norway, CO₂e emissions would still be lower than those scenarios using road trucks (Bane Nor, 2022; Solheim et al., 2025). The study of Boschiero et al. (2019) investigated post-harvest GHG emissions from Italian apples. The study considered exports to Norway and showed that the cumulative energy demand and GHG emissions could be significantly reduced if most transport from Bolzano (South Tyrol) to Oslo were carried out by train instead of semi-trailer trucks. Moreover, this study calculated that a total of 1,780 km could be covered by train. With Italy being the main apple exporter (56,1 %) into Norway, this would significantly improve the

Table 11
CO₂ emissions from different import countries. The values account only for the part from the importing country to the Oslo main distribution centre.

Country	New Zealand	Chile	Italy	Poland	Austria	Import
CO ₂ e / tonnes	503.8	685.0	3,472.8	832.5	197.8	5,691.9
Spec. CO ₂ e	0.3696	0.2629	0.1597	0.1108	0.1405	0.1644

carbon footprint of apples available in Norway. Moreover, this underlines that reducing the carbon footprint of food imports is a cross-border challenge and that decarbonization requires coordinated changes in transport systems and policies throughout the entire international supply chain, beyond Norway’s borders.

Table 12 shows the CO₂e for the three main supermarket chains, based on the 97 % share. Chain C has the highest share of sold apples (45.4 %), and naturally a higher share of CO₂ emissions. However, when considering the specific CO₂e emission/kg CO₂e/kg apples sold, the specific emissions were in the same range as for the other two chains with 0.161, 0.174 and 0.166 respectively. However, the shares of apples sold for chain A and B were substantially lower with 24.8 % and 29.8 %, compared to chain C. It can be assumed that the lower specific CO₂e emissions was due to the difference in the regional distribution structure of chain C (Figs. 6; 8). Supermarket C has 13 zones with 13 regional distribution centres, and this division into smaller zones reduces the distances from distribution centres to supermarkets.

A recent study looked into the energy consumption of Norwegian packaging plants and found an average specific energy use between 85–512 kWh per tonnes apples for four different packaging plants during apple season (Indergård et al., 2024). This leads to an additional carbon footprint for the in Norway produced apples of 0.0026 kg CO₂e per kg apples for the best plant to 0.0154 kg CO₂e per kg apples for the worst, assumed a footprint of 30·10⁻³ kg CO₂e/kWh for Norway’s electrical grid (Ember, 2025). Compared to the hypothetical inland case, displayed in Table 13 with a specific CO₂ footprint of 0.045 kg CO₂e per kg apples, we can see that the number for storage can be quite significant if the packaging plant has a high consumption of electricity. If the packaging plant has low electricity usage, the storage has only low significance. This is valid for the low carbon footprint of electricity in Norway, looking on the specific CO₂ emissions per kWh in countries with less renewable energy like Germany with 371 ·10⁻³ kg CO₂e per kWh in 2023 (Ember, 2025), the significance even for low electric energy consuming plants is high.

If, hypothetically, all apples would be imported from abroad, the total specific CO₂ footprint per kg apples would rise to 0.195 CO₂e (Table 14). This would be significantly higher than the current scenario (Table 12) as well as the hypothetical scenario of only inland apples (Table 13). This suggests that most emissions are due to transport into Norway. Moreover, our study indirectly considered empty runs, meaning the movement of empty containers back to the country of origin. A study on avocados reported that the transport back from Port of Rotterdam to the cold store in Cape town, South Africa, accounted for 35.7 % of the total carbon footprint of the fruit (du Plessis et al., 2025). How this empty transportation can be optimised or avoided altogether should be a factor, when optimising the cold supply chain of products. In general, the distribution of apples and other fruits is quite complex, as multiple stakeholders from different countries are involved within the system. It makes it extremely difficult to calculate end-to-end emissions, considering the complex logistics, differences in each country and availability of data (du Plessis et al., 2025).

3.6. Limitations of the study

While this study provides valuable insights into refrigerated transport of apples in and into Norway, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations resulting from methodological and practical considerations.

It must be noted that the emissions from the operation of warehouses like energy use, refrigerant leakage, intern transportation, packaging and waste management were not included in this study. As a result, the emission estimates for supermarket chain C may be overestimated, since the chain operates less warehouses and would likely have lower emissions from operating the facilities. However, this may be offset by higher transport-related emissions due to longer distribution distances. Furthermore, the actual transport chain within exporting countries,

Fig. 7. Specific CO₂ footprint for all supermarkets of the three main supermarket chains in Norway.

from farmers to packing plants and subsequent steps leading to port of export, were not considered in this study. This part of the transport chain could significantly influence the emissions attributed to different exporting countries and, consequently, affect decisions about which country is the most suitable source of imports from an emissions perspective.

The transport between farmers and packing plants inside Norway was not considered, it has a similar complexity as the distribution from distribution centres to the supermarkets but the information about the location and transported amounts is requiring detailed examination of multiple sources and is not publicly available.

Parts of the Transport chain has already been through emission reduction measures, which were not considered in this study, due to its complexity. One example is one of the distribution companies, which has a fleet of a total of 700 trucks (400 owned and 300 rented). In this fleet most trucks operate on fossil fuel (Euro6) but 108 are electrical trucks, 4 are hydrogen driven trucks and 37 do run on biogas. The distribution in Oslo is all electrical, and by 2026 it is planned that all trucks are fossil free.

Supermarket chain A operates partly on its own trucks but have also a cooperation with the above-mentioned distribution company, and some other transport companies for some of the regions. The trucks are mainly Euro6-trucks, but chain A distribution has invested in 3 larger electrical trucks and 12 biogas driven trucks. By 2026 it is planned that all self-owned trucks will be fossil-free and all external trucks by 2030

(Bama, 2023b). It will be important to assess whether these goals can be achieved by 2026 and to evaluate the extent of emissions reduction that can be accomplished.

The real share of different working fluids inside the refrigeration units remains largely undefined. In the maritime sector it is possible to bypass penalties by buying phased out refrigerants from countries not part of relevant policies. Moreover, real leakage rates represent one of the greatest uncertainties in the refrigeration segment of the supply chain.

In this work it was assumed that the COP of the refrigeration units is constant with a value of two. In reality the COP is heavily temperature dependent especially for the maritime refrigeration units, that can experience temperature on board of the ship of up to 50 °C (Lawton et al., 2025). In this study the temperature in 2 m elevation was taken for every route and that must not be the temperature the refrigeration unit is experiencing.

The reader must note, that in this study it was assumed that all the chains have the same profile of importing countries and shares between them, this is not necessarily the case.

4. Conclusions and future outlook

The methodology developed in this study provides a reproducible framework for calculating emissions associated with food commodities, thereby enhancing the transparency of the food supply chain. It is

Fig. 8. Specific CO₂e footprint for all supermarkets of the three main supermarket chains in Norway. Yellow indicates low specific CO₂e emissions, while red indicates high specific CO₂e emissions. The coloration of the zones represents average values across each zone.

Table 12

CO₂e for the entire transportation (import + domestic distribution) for chain A, chain C and chain B.

	All	Chain A	Chain B	Chain C
CO ₂ e Emissions / tonnes	7,432	1,842	3,268	2,323
Tonnes Apples	44,823	11,115	20,345	13,356
Share Apple Selling / %	100	24.8	45.4	29.8
Share CO ₂ e emissions	100	24.8	44.0	31.3
Spec. CO ₂ e emission / kg CO ₂ e/kg Apples	0.166	0.166	0.161	0.1739

Table 13

Inland: if all apples would have been produced in Norway (same production profile).

	All	Transport	Refrigeration	Leakage
Spec. CO ₂ e emission / kg CO ₂ e/kg Apples	0.045	0.044	0.0001	0.001
Share / %	100	97.0	0.2	2.8

important to note that this methodology is based on certain assumptions, which arise from a lack of comprehensive information and the challenges associated with obtaining information due to the high number of stakeholders in the market.

To conclude, mapping emissions connected to the transportation and refrigeration of fruits presents significant challenges, due to a complex macro-system and differences in reporting emission data, study scopes, and data availability. The study showed a mean carbon footprint of 0.166 kg CO₂e per kg apples, whereof 97.3 % was caused directly due transport, 1.8 % due to refrigerant leakage and only 0.9 % due to the refrigeration itself. A total of 76.6 % of the emissions were tracked outside of Norway and thus only 23.4 % originating from supply chain inside Norway. To further decarbonise the apple supply chain, it is advisable to increase domestic apple production in Norway and extend the storage durations by using controlled-atmosphere storage technologies to extend postharvest storage durations. As Norway’s electricity grid is almost entirely powered by renewable energy, the associated

GHG emissions from long-term storage would be minimal. This would help expanding the availability of local apples throughout a greater portion of the year, significantly reduce GHG emissions related to import and strengthen local value creation and self-sufficiency. Trying to reduce the imported amounts of apples from New Zealand and Chile can also help reducing the CO₂ footprint of transportation. Shifting refrigerants to more climate friendly alternatives, like natural working fluids, will significantly decrease emissions related to leakages. Further, it is advantageous to prioritise ship transport and train travel to the greatest extent possible. It is essential for policymakers to invest in the development of improved and more reliable transportation networks, as well as to optimise the utilisation of existing rail lines by increasing service frequency to their maximum capacity.

For future work, the framework should be expanded to include additional fruits and vegetables, such as bananas, melons, carrots, tomatoes, and onions, as these represent the largest consumption groups in Norway (Kendler et al., 2025). Furthermore, it is essential to consider the decarbonisation measures already implemented, as well as the supply chain network inside the exporting countries.

Declaration of generative AI in scientific writing

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT and CoPilot in order to improve language and spell check the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication

Table 14

Import: if all apples would have been imported (same import profile).

	All	Transport	Refrigeration	Leakage
Spec. CO ₂ e emission / kg CO ₂ e/kg Apples	0.195	0.190	0.002	0.003
Share / %	100	97.3	0.8	1.8

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patrick Hadamitzky: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sophie Kendler:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kristina Norne Widell:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Erlend Indergård:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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